

Micellization and conductance behaviour of dysprosium myristate and stearate soaps in methanol

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Abstract : The critical micelle concentration (CMC) of dysprosium soaps (myristate and stearate) in methanol have been determined by conductometric measurement. The value of CMC decreases with increasing chain length of fatty acid component. The molar conductance at infinite dilution, and degree of ionisation have been evaluated. The results show that dysprosium soaps behave as weak electrolytes.

Keywords : Dysprosium myristate soap, Dysprosium stearate soap, micelle.

The study of metallic soaps is becoming increasingly important in industrial as well as in academic fields¹. The physico-chemical characteristics and structure of these soaps depend on the method and conditions of preparation.

The present work discusses the conductometric studies of solutions of dysprosium soaps (myristate and stearate) in methanol to examine their micellar behaviour and the nature of the soap in non-aqueous media.

Results and discussion

The specific conductance, k of the solution of dysprosium soaps (myristate and stearate) in methanol increases with increasing concentration and decreasing chain length of the soap¹. The increase in specific conductance may be due to dysprosium soaps behave as simple electrolytes in dilute solutions and are ionised into simple metal cations, Dy^{3+} , and fatty acid anions, $RCOO^-$ (where R is $C_{13}H_{27}$ and $C_{17}H_{35}$ for myristate and stearate). The decrease in specific conductance with increasing chain length of the soap may be due to increasing size and decreasing mobility of anions in the soap molecule. It may be pointed out that the micellization process in organic solvents is somewhat different from that in aqueous solutions. The aggregation begins at very low concentration in organic solvent and results in the formation of very much smaller aggregate.

The main cause of micellization in organic solvent is the energy change due to dipole-dipole interaction between the polar groups of soap molecules.

The plots of specific conductance vs soap concentration (Fig. 1) in methanol are characterized by intersection of two straight lines at definite soap concentrations, 4.7×10^{-3} and $4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, molar conduc-

Fig. 1. Specific conductance vs concentration of dysprosium soaps : (●) myristate, (▲) stearate.

tance 1.11 and 2.65 mho cm² mol⁻¹; K 11.8×10^{-7} and 2.4×10^{-7} respectively corresponding to the CMC of dysprosium myristate and dysprosium stearate respectively. It is suggested that the soap is considerably ionized in dilute solutions and anions begin to aggregate to form ionic micelles at CMC. The result shows that CMC decrease with increasing chain length of the soap molecule.

Molar conductance and ionisation constant :

The molar conductance, μ of the solutions of dysprosium soaps in methanol decreases with increasing concentration and chain length of the soap. The decrease may be attributed to the combined effects of the ionic atmosphere, solvation of ions, decrease of mobility and formation of micelles. The plots of molar conductance μ vs square root of soap concentration $c^{1/2}$ (Fig. 2) are concave upwards, indicating that the soaps behave as weak electrolytes in dilute solutions. The limiting molar conductance μ_0 of these soap solutions cannot be obtained by the usual extrapolation method and the Debye-Huckel-Onsager equation is not applicable to these soap solutions in methanol. The soaps in dilute solutions behave as

weak electrolytes and so an expression for the ionization of dysprosium soaps can be developed using the Ostwald model. If c is the concentration in mol/lit and α is the degree of ionization of the soaps, the equivalent concentration of different species can be represented as

where $\text{R} = \text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{27}$ and $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}$ for myristate and stearate, respectively.

The ionisation constant, K can be expressed as :

$$K = 27c^3\alpha^4/(1 - \alpha) \tag{1}$$

Since the number of ions for a weak electrolyte in dilute solutions is relatively small and interionic effects are almost negligible the activities of ions may be taken as proportional to the concentration and the conductance ratio (Arrhenius dissociation), μ/μ_0 , is reasonably good measure for the degree of ionization α (where μ is the molar conductance at finite concentration and μ_0 is the molar conductance at infinite dilution). On substituting the value of α and rearranging eq. (1), one obtains

$$\mu^3c^3 = \frac{K\mu_0^4}{27\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^3}{27} \tag{2}$$

The values of the ionisation constant, K , and μ_0 can be obtained from the slope ($K\mu_0^4/27$) and intercept ($-K\mu_0^3/27$) of the linear portion of the plots of μ^3c^3 vs $1/\mu$ (Fig. 3) for dilute soap solutions. The values of the degree of ionization α at different soap concentrations have been calculated by assuming that it is equal to the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 . The low values of the degree of ionization α show that the solutions of dysprosium soaps in methanol behave as weak electrolytes. The degree of ionization decreases rapidly in dilute solutions with increasing soap concentration whereas the values of α decrease slowly above the CMC. The values of the ionization constant, K have been calculated by using eq. (1) and assuming the degree of ionization as equal to the conductance ratio. The values of K remain nearly constant with increase in the soap concentration below the CMC, as expected for weak electrolytes, but increase above the CMC. The increase in the values of ionization constant above the CMC may be partly due to the fact that the conductance ratio μ/μ_0 is not exactly equal to the degree of ionization, α but mainly due to the fact that activity co-efficient of ions are not exactly equal to unity. The deviations observed at higher soap concentrations in methanol from the Debye-

Fig. 2. Molar conductance vs square root of concentration of dysprosium soap in methanol : (●) stearate, (▲) myristate.

Fig. 3. $\mu^3 c^3$ vs $1/\mu$ of dysprosium soaps in methanol : (●) stearate, (▲) myristate.

Huckel treatment are in agreement with the Bjerrum and Fuoss and Kraus extensions of the Debye-Huckel theory.

The results show that the soaps behave as weak elec-

trolytes in dilute solutions below the CMC and the conductance results can be explained on the basis of Debye-Huckel theory and the Ostwald's formula of weak electrolytes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H./A.R. grade. Solvent methanol was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Dysprosium soap (myristate and stearate) were synthesised as mentioned in our earlier communication². The metal soaps thus obtained were recrystallized twice from methanol and dried under vacuum for at least 48 h before use.

The conductance of soap solutions in methanol was measured with digital conductivity meter (Toshniwal CL 01.10 A) and dipping type conductivity cell with platinised electrodes (cell constant 0.875) at 40 ± 0.05 °C in a thermostat.

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